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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

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доктор медицинских наук, доцент, заведующий кафедрой
Гистологии, цитологии и эмбриологии Самаркандского
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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144

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доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Детской
хирургии Самаркандского государственного медицинского
университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0003-2650-4445

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дерматовенерология и СПИД, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-3022-916X

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кандидат медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Факультетской
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медицинского института.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327

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кандидат медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Педиатрии,
неонатологии и протекции детских болезней №2
Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергеновна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Ташкентского государственного
стоматологического института
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры
онкологии Самаркандского государственного
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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

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ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

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*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Tashkent State Dental Institute
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Rahimov Nodir Maxammatkulovich

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ISLAMOVA Nilufar Bustanovna
NAZAROVA Nodira Sharipovna
Associate Professor
Samarkand State Medical University

RESEARCH CASES IN WOMEN AFTER MENOPAUSE CLINICAL AND MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN ORAL ORGANS AND THEIR ANALYSIS

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ANNOTATION

Objective: to study the clinical and microbiological manifestations and mechanisms of development of dental diseases in postmenopausal women.

Methods: we examined 40 postmenopausal women with various diseases of the oral cavity. The control group of patients were women who are not in the postmenopausal period with dental diseases.

Results: All participants of the study underwent a comprehensive examination: hygienic and periodontal indices (OHI-S hygiene index, PI periodontal index), pH of mixed saliva was measured, sialometry was performed according to the method of M.M. Pozharitskaya, studied the microflora of the oral cavity by PCR (polymerase chain reaction).

Conclusions: Thus, the greater sensitivity of the above indices is associated with the peculiarities of the pathogenesis of menopause, namely with estrogen deficiency. The content of estrogen receptors on the oral mucosa plays a direct role in the development of dental diseases

Keywords: menopause, generalized periodontitis, postmenopausal period, diseases of the oral mucosa.

ИСЛАМОВА Нилуфар Бустановна
НАЗАРОВА Нодира Шариповна
Доцент

Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет

КЛИНИКО-МОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ ОРГАНОВ И ТКАНЕЙ ПОЛОСТИ РТА У ЖЕНЩИН ПОСЛЕ МЕНОПАУЗЫ И ИХ АНАЛИЗ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Цель: изучить клинические и микробиологические проявления и механизмы развития стоматологических заболеваний у женщин в постменопаузе.

Методы: мы обследовали 40 женщин в постменопаузе с различными заболеваниями полости рта. Контрольную группу пациенток составили женщины, не находящиеся в постменопаузальном периоде с заболеваниями зубов.

Результаты: Всем участникам исследования было проведено комплексное обследование: гигиенические и пародонтальные показатели (ОНИ-S гигиенический индекс, PI пародонтальный индекс), измерен pH смешанной слюны, проведена сиалометрия по методу М.М. Пожарицкой, изучена микрофлора полости рта методом ПЦР (полимеразная цепная реакция).

Выводы: Таким образом, большая чувствительность вышеуказанных показателей связана с особенностями патогенеза менопаузы, а именно с дефицитом эстрогенов. Содержание рецепторов эстрогена на слизистой оболочке полости рта играет непосредственную роль в развитии стоматологических заболеваний

Ключевые слова: менопауза, генерализованный пародонтит, постменопаузальный период, заболевания слизистой оболочки полости рта.

Исламова Нилуфар Бустановна
Назарова Нодира Шариповна

доцент

Самарканд Давлат Тиббиёт Университети

ПОСТМЕНОПАУЗА ДАВРИДАГИ АЁЛЛАРДА ОҒИЗ БЎШЛИҒИ АЪЗОЛАРИ ВА ТЎҚИМАЛАРИНИНГ КЛИНИК ВА МОРФОЛОГИК ЎЗГАРИШЛАРИ ВА УЛАРНИ ТАҲЛИЛ ҚИЛИШ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Мақсад: Постменопауза давридаги аёлларда стоматологик касалликларининг клиник ва микробиологик кўринишлари ва ривожланиш механизмларини ўрганиш.

Усуллари: биз оғиз бўшлиғининг турли касалликлари бўлган 40 постменопауза давридаги аёлларни текширдик. Беморларнинг назорат гуруҳи тиш касалликлари билан постменопауза даврида бўлмаган аёллар эди.

Натижалар: тадқиқотнинг барча иштирокчилари кенг қамровли текширувдан ўтдилар: гигиеник ва пародонтал индекслар (ОҲИ-с гигиена индекси, ПИ пародонтал индекс), аралаш сўлак қиймати ўлчанди, сиалометрия М. М. Пожарицкая усули бўйича ўтказилди, ПСР орқали оғиз бўшлиғининг микрофлорасини ўрганди (полимераза занжири реакцияси).

Хулоса: шундай қилиб, юқоридаги индексларнинг катта сезгирлиги менопауза патогенезининг ўзига хос хусусиятлари, яъни эстроген етишмовчилиги билан боғлиқ. Оғиз мукозасидаги эстроген рецепторлари таркиби стоматологик касалликларининг ривожланишида бевосита рол ўйнайди

Калит сўзлар: менопауза, умумий пародонтит, постменопауза даври, оғиз бўшлиғи шиллик қавати касалликлари.

Introduction. The postmenopausal period of women's life is characterized by metabolic disorders in various tissues, including the dentition, in the form of tooth loss, periodontal disease, increased resorption of the alveolar and jaw bones. The high prevalence of dental diseases in postmenopausal women and the difficulties encountered in their treatment and prevention are largely due to insufficient knowledge of the pathogenesis. In recent years, a large number of works have been devoted to studying the nature of the relationship between systemic osteoporosis and generalized periodontitis, however, the available information is contradictory and requires additional research.

For practitioners, there is a question of choosing an adequate complex therapy for chronic generalized periodontitis in postmenopausal women. Given that bone resorption processes prevail in osteoporosis, certain features should be assumed when planning the treatment of chronic generalized periodontitis in such cases.

One of the likely etiological factors is low bone mineral density of the facial skeleton in the postmenopausal period (Norderyd O.M. et al., 2013).

At present, there are practically no substantiated data on the use of medications that correct mineral metabolism in the complex treatment of periodontitis, in particular, there is not enough data on the effect of antiresorptive drugs on osteogenesis of the alveolar bone.

Studies of dentists and osteologists have determined the role of hypoestrogenemia in postmenopausal women in the development of systemic osteoporosis and pathological processes in periodontal tissues.

It has been noted that systemic osteoporosis caused by estrogen deficiency in menopausal women extends to the dentition. This is manifested in a decrease in the height of the tops of the interdental septa, the appearance of foci of osteoporosis in the body of the lower jaw, and a decrease in the density of the alveolar process (E.C.Shen, C.H.Gau, Y.D.Hsieh et al., 2014). At the same time, the nature of the development of inflammatory periodontal diseases in postmenopausal women, its structure, prevalence, and clinical and diagnostic features have not been studied enough.

The purpose of the study: to study the clinical and microbiological manifestations and mechanisms of development of dental diseases in postmenopausal women.

Material and methods: we examined 40 postmenopausal women with various diseases of the oral cavity. The control group of patients were women who are not in the postmenopausal period with dental diseases.

Results and discussions: All participants of the study underwent a comprehensive examination: hygienic and periodontal indices (OHI-S hygiene index, PI periodontal index), pH of mixed saliva was measured, sialometry was performed according to the method of M.M. Pozharitskaya, studied the microflora of the oral cavity by PCR (polymerase chain reaction).

When collecting anamnesis, it was revealed that most often women of group I complained of bleeding gums (13.3%) and bad breath (6.7%). Group II patients complained of bleeding gums (66%), bad breath (43.9%), exposure of the roots of the teeth (15.3%), tooth mobility (16.1%), and 40% of women had complaints of dry mouth. While 26.7% of postmenopausal women taking HRT complained of bleeding gums, 18.1% complained of dry mouth and bad breath.

According to the results of the survey, postmenopausal women taking HRT 2.3 times less complained of bleeding gums (27.7%) and dry mouth (17.1%) compared with women not taking HRT (63%; 40% respectively). 18.1% of women taking HRT noted bad breath, which is 2.5 times less than women not taking HRT (43.9%), but 3 times more than in the control group (5.8%). Postmenopausal women, regardless of whether they take HRT or not, were 3 times more likely to have a white coating on the tongue (18.1%, 15.3%, respectively) than women in the control group (6.7%). Burning sensation in the oral cavity was noted by 5.7% of women in group II and 3.9% in group III.

Attention was also paid to the TMJ, noting the symmetry of the face and movements of the mandible when opening the mouth, pain when moving the mandible, and the range of vertical and lateral movements of the mandible. In 22.6% of group I, 49, in 40% of group II and 45.7% of group III women, a deviation was observed, manifested by a displacement of the lower jaw to the side at the beginning and a return to the midline in the middle of opening the mouth by 2 mm. None of the subjects had limited range of vertical and lateral movements. 2.9% - group I, 14.3% - group II and 11.5% - group III sometimes noted clicks during the movement of the lower jaw.

When examining the oral cavity, such non-carious lesions of the teeth as erosion were noted, which were detected in 2.8% of women in group II. Wedge-shaped defects were noted in 17.1% of group I, 54.3% of group II and 62.8% of group III women. Pathological tooth wear was detected in 17.1% of group II and 14.2% of group III women, but there were no significant differences between the groups ($p > 0.05$).

The clinical examination included the determination of the KPU index, the OHI-S hygiene index, the periodontal index PI, the measurement of the pH of the mixed saliva, sialometry, and the assessment of the microflora of the oral cavity by PCR (polymerase chain reaction).

In the study of the intensity of tooth decay by caries, it was found that in group I, the average value of the KPU index = 13.58 ± 6.35 (moderate level of caries intensity), in group II, KPU = 18.8

± 6.17 (very high level of caries intensity) , and in group III, the KPU index = 16.45 ± 6.2 (high level of caries intensity).

When examining the level of oral hygiene, it was found that the OHI-S hygiene index, which takes into account both the amount of plaque and tartar, in group I was 1.83 ± 1.1 , in group II - 2.89 ± 0.89 , in group III - 3.24 ± 1.6 . A statistically significant difference was found between groups I and II, groups II and III ($p < 0.05$), and between groups I and III there were no significant differences in relation to the values of group parameters ($p > 0.05$).

To determine the severity of periodontal disease, the periodontal index PI was used, which showed that its value in women who do not take HRT is 2.31 ± 1.29 , which corresponds to the average degree of periodontal pathology and is 2 times more than in women taking HRT and 5 times more than in the control group. In women taking HRT, the value of the periodontal index PI is 1.16 ± 0.75 , which corresponds to the initial and mild degree of periodontal pathology, and in the control group - 0.46 ± 0.56 .

An objective examination of patients showed increased saliva viscosity, combined with foaminess in 51.4% of women not taking HRT, and in 25.7% of women taking HRT.

Sialometry according to the method of M.M. Pozharitskaya allows you to determine the amount of mixed unstimulated saliva. The greatest hyposalivation in the oral cavity was observed in women not taking HRT, and the average for the group was 2.1 ± 0.28 ml at a rate of 4.1 ml.

In the study of the pH of mixed saliva in women in group I, the average value reached 7.04 ± 0.35 , in group II, $\text{pH} = 6.48 \pm 0.33$, and in group III, the average $\text{pH} = 6.94 \pm 0.36$.

Analysis of samples of the contents of periodontal pockets showed that *A. actinomycetemcomitans*, a gram-negative non-motile facultative anaerobic coccobacillus, was found in 22.9% of women in group I, 51.4% in group II and 37.1% in group III. It was found that *A. actinomycetemcomitans* occurs 1.4 times more often in women who do not take HRT compared to women taking it and 2.2 times more often than in the control group. At the same time, a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) is observed only between groups I and II.

The frequency of occurrence of *T. denticola*, which is able to organize associations with other bacteria, especially with *P. gingivalis* and *T. forsythia*, is 37.1% in group I, 54.3% in group II and 51.4% in group III, but no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between groups was found. *T. forsythia*, which most strongly promotes cell apoptosis, was found in 51.4% in group I, in 80% in group II, and in 45.7% in group III. A significant difference was found between groups I and II, II and III. Periodontopathogen *P. gingivalis*, as the most aggressive bacterium, was found in 11.4% of women in group I, 77.1% in group II and 28.6% in group III, respectively. It was shown that *P. gingivalis* occurs 6.7 times more often in group II than in group I and 2.7 times more often than in group III.

P. intermedia was found in 11.3% of women in group I, in 74.3% in group II and in 25.7% in group III, respectively. *P. intermedia* is 6.6 times more common in group II than in group I and 2.9 times more common than in group III. At the same time, there is a significant difference between *P. gingivalis* and *P. intermedia* ($p < 0.05$) between groups I and II, II and III. There was no significant difference between the qualitative composition of the microflora of periodontal pockets in groups I and III (control and the group of women taking HRT) ($p > 0.05$).

Most often, in women not taking HRT, *P. gingivalis*, *P. intermedia*, and *T. forsythia* were detected, in contrast to women taking HRT. *A. actinomycetemcomitans* and *T. denticola* as part of the subgingival microflora were found regardless of the use of HRT and were detected in a smaller number of patients.

The study also revealed Epstein-Barr virus in 11.4% of women in group I, 20% in group II and 17.1% in group III. Herpes simplex virus was found in 17.1% of the women of group I, 25.7% of group II and 28.6% of group III. *Candida albicans* was found in 5.7% of women of group I, 25.7% of group II and 20% of group III, and a significant difference was found between groups I and II, II and III ($p < 0.05$).

In all patients of the control group, in whom a periodontopathogen was detected, the amount was relatively low and did not exceed 105 units/ml.

Spearman's rank correlation method was used to identify the relationship between the degree of clinical indicators and the composition of the microflora of periodontal pockets.

The relationship between an increased number of *A. actinomycetemcomitans* in the contents of the periodontal pocket with a low level of oral hygiene according to the OHI-S index ($r=0.503027$) and with the severity of periodontitis ($r=0.505208$) was revealed. A negative correlation was observed with the pH of the mixed saliva ($r=-0.456773$).

T. denticola. No correlation was found between the amount of *T. denticola* in periodontal pockets and clinical parameters.

P. gingivalis. The content of *P. gingivalis* moderately correlated with the level of oral hygiene ($r=0.469771$). A negative relationship between the content of *P. gingivalis* and the pH of mixed saliva ($r=-0.491576$) was revealed.

T. forsythia

The amount of *T. forsythia* in the contents of periodontal pockets moderately correlated with the level of oral hygiene ($r=0.376309$), and to a greater extent with the severity of periodontitis ($r=0.552702$). A negative correlation was also found with the pH of the mixed saliva. *P. intermedia*. The level of *P. intermedia* depended on the severity of periodontitis ($r=0.416681$).

According to the results of the study, a statistically significant relationship was revealed between oral hygiene and the severity of periodontitis with the quantitative composition of periodontopathogens of group II ($p < 0.05$).

Findings.

1. Thus, the greater sensitivity of the above indices is associated with the peculiarities of the pathogenesis of menopause, namely with estrogen deficiency. The content of estrogen receptors on the oral mucosa plays a direct role in the development of dental diseases.
2. During menopause, the angioprotective effect of estrogens weakens, followed by damage to the structures of the hemomicrocirculatory bed. Also during this period, the production of osteoclasts increases, the production of osteoblasts decreases, the absorption of calcium in the intestine decreases, the lack of vitamin D, which leads to increased bone resorption.
3. Due to estrogen deficiency, there is a decrease in intestinal absorption of calcium in the body, which in turn leads to disturbances in the regulation of calcium-phosphate metabolism and increased calcium release not only into the blood serum, but also into saliva. Therefore, a high concentration of calcium in the saliva of menopausal women can lead to faster plaque mineralization and, consequently, to an increase in stone formation, which has a direct impact on the progression of gingivitis and periodontitis. Thus, the pathogenesis of menopause affects the state of all structures of the oral cavity.

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БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

8 ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

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Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
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